

SILENCE WILL NOT BE RIGHT

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Topic Human Rights

Annotation: This article focuses on protecting women from harassment and violence. The purpose of this article is to regulate relations in the field of protecting women from all forms of harassment and violence.

Key concepts: Protection of women, protection order, zero tolerance for violence.

Women and men have equal rights

(Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

A victim of harassment and is entitled to:

- appeal to the authorized bodies and organization or court with a statement of commission in relation to the charge of committing a crime or a crime against their commission;
- obtaining the results of consideration, economic, social, psychological, medical and other assistance in special centers, as well as in connection with a specific telephone line;
- applying to the internal affairs bodies with a request to issue a protection order, and in case of violation of the conditions of the protection order, informing them about it;
- applying to the court with a claim for compensation for material damage caused to her and compensation for moral damage as a result of harassment and violence;
- the victim of harassment and violence, when applying to the court with an application for compensation for material damage caused to him and compensation for moral damage, is exempt from paying the state free.

(Article 4. Rights of the victim of harassment and violence)

The main directions of state policy in the field of protecting women from harassment and violence are:

- development and implementation of gender policy, government programs and strategies to protect women from harassment and violence;
- creating in society an atmosphere of intolerance towards oppression and violence against women;
- ensuring the protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of women from oppression and violence;
- increase in society of legal consciousness and legal culture, strengthening the rule of law;
- creation of effective organizational and legal mechanism for the prevention, detection, suppression of harassment and violence against women;
- taking measures to eliminate the causes and conditions conducive to harassment and violence against women;
- ensuring cooperation between state bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations and other civil society institutions in order to prevent harassment and violence.

(Article 5. The main directions of state policy in the field of protecting women from harassment and violence)

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Violence against women and children can be understood as pressure, coercion, the use of physical force or coercive influence on someone. This problem occurs in all societies and at all times, and it was considered as part of the moral, ethical, religious norms that carried elements of education or control. Thus, the justification or condemnation of violence depends on the social culture, religion, society in which people live, and, accordingly, depending on this, it can increase or decrease.

Violence against the two most vulnerable segments of the population in Uzbekistan, including domestic violence, is becoming a serious and widespread problem that gives rise to many other social and individual problems. We believe that is necessary not only to punish the perpetrators, but also to rehabilitate the victim of violence and to work with the person who committed the violence in order to avoid the recurrence of such cases.

In most cases, we observe that women, sometimes even children, are subjected to violent actions by family members. The consequences of domestic violence are bodily harm, mental disorders, suicide, as well as loss of self-esteem in the victim. Observations of doctors show that there are more cases when frequent bullying and rude attitude promotes and provokes violent responses in the victim towards the aggressor.

Victims of violence can obtain a protection order for public protection from perpetrators of harassment or violence against women.

This warrant is issued on the basis of an appeal from the victim on information received from individuals or legal entities, including those disseminated in the media and (or) social networks.

The basis for extradition may be: direct identification of cases or attempts of violence, harassment by authorized bodies and organizations, as well as materials received from state bodies and other organizations. A preventive inspector can issue a protection order.

The term of the protection order is issued for 30 days. At the end of the term, it can be extended for another 30 days.

(Also, this is set out in Article 23. Issuance and renewal of a protection order)

- Who in our state is responsible for the policy on women and the enactment of these laws?

- Parliament – considers Legislative acts, is also empowered to make laws. As far as the issue of women is concerned, their duty was assigned to the Ministry of Mahalla.

We need a separate structure that will deal specifically with women and children, and not push them into other institutions that already have a lot of their own responsibilities.

We need a separate ministry of social protection, which we also do not have as such.

-Why don't our Legislative bodies improve the laws in the direction of violence?

- Legislative bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan do not establish tougher laws in the fight against violence.

It appears as a kind of rule of the “natural consequence of selection”

- How can the state be changed in terms of this direction?

- The state will change gradually, step by step, being in development. Need to gain experience and learn from foreign countries.

- Does our religion and mentality matter in this?

- If we talk about religion, then in our beautiful religion of Islam there is no way to underestimate the status of woman, to mock and beat his wife. No matter how those same “sacred” people direct dirty water, shouting about the complete obedience of a woman to a men, then not with such a cruel meaning. In the religion of Islam, special attention is paid to women. They are elevated to the most beautiful, with a call to please, protect and protect from all ailments.

Mentality – way of thinking, mindset and perception in general.

There is a certain stereotype about a patriarchal society. For instance, the wife endures all negative ailments, while she does not turn to anyone, because her parents will not allow her to live, and the woman is afraid to go to any institution, but she is afraid of the following consequences of her husband.

We can conclude: All international recommendations boil down to the fact that domestic violence should be criminalized. Criminalized, so it should be listed as a crime in the criminal code.

At the same time, in these cases, a code of administrative responsibility is being considered from 3 minimum, to administrative arrest up to 15 days.

There is not concept of domestic violence in Uzbek legislation.

This should be singled out in a separate category of crimes. It should immediately be punished under the criminal code.

We need to create an atmosphere of intolerance towards violence in society.

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